

Rural Women's Participation of Local Development: A Case of the Women Shareholders of Vakifli Development Cooperative

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author EO designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author MU managed the analyses and the literature searches of the study. Author NK managed the survey studies. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/AJAEES/2017/33435

Editor(s):

(1) Roxana Plesa, University of Petrosani, Romania.

Reviewers:

(1) Gabriela Civeira, University of Moron, Argentina.

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(3) O. Murat Koçturk, Celal Bayar University, Manisa, Turkey.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19057>

Original Research Article

Received 15th April 2017

Accepted 6th May 2017

Published 15th May 2017

ABSTRACT

Agricultural cooperatives play an important role in supporting small agricultural producers and marginalized groups such as young people and women. They empower their members economically and socially and create sustainable rural employment through business models that are resilient to economic and environmental shocks.

Women are represented in various forms and types of cooperatives in Turkey, but, the ratio of women membership in agricultural cooperatives is extremely low. Women in rural cooperatives often produce food items and handicrafts. The mind-sets of cooperative members are often not oriented toward the consumers or the market. Taking pride in their products, they struggle with valuing their products according to consumer tastes rather than the quality of their homemaking skills. These products may be intended for the local market or for export. For local market, a key issue is

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transport to urban areas. For export, it is important to build relationships with reliable partners. In term of the activities performed by women, in 2004, a cooperative founded in which Vakıflı village of Hatay province has a unique characteristics called Turkey's change makers. Our paper focus on the activities, economic and social acquisitions implemented obtained by women's branch of Vakıflı Development Cooperative. We also investigate social and economic returns in terms of the cooperative's members and inhabitants of village. Thus, we aim to evaluation alternative solutions (especially for rural areas suffered from large population migration) taking into account a case, Vakıflı Development Cooperative. To reach study aims, we conducted face to face interviews using by full census method with women shareholders of Vakıflı Development Cooperative.

Keywords: Agricultural cooperatives; local development; women.

1. INTRODUCTION

Should the rural development is regarded as a whole, some of the crucial parts of this whole can be said to be taken as the basis in this study. One of these is the rural migration and constitutes one of the basic parameters of this study. Migration from rural areas to cities is a subject which is discussed and studied a lot; however, it is still a complicating problem. If the littleness of the rural population is an indication of being developed, the migration should happen. On the other hand unqualified rural employment movement to cities reveals such adverse results that the requirement of keeping people in their settlements has become an issue of concern and haste for those responsible to find solutions. In this case, migration from rural areas to cities requires multidimensional, comprehensive, detailed, micro based efforts as well as the macro based ones.

Another parameter that makes this study important is the rural women. Field researches and macro parameters indicate the role of women in terms of the rural society, society as a whole, agricultural production and the general economy as much as their role that doesn't correspond to these parameters. Women in rural areas are a human source that is used below their capacity and forced to be unqualified due to the reasons such as inadequate education and lack of development environment. Finding the position for rural women in the qualified human capital of the country requires a lot of effort.

Another starting point of this study is getting organized in rural areas and entrepreneurship. Getting organized is a structure that has not been able to complete its process from the current direction to the direction it is supposed to follow since the establishment of the Republic of Turkey. Requirements for a stronger organization in rural areas were set forth and solutions were

determined to spread it in a period of almost every five years; however, it was managed to bring it to somewhere close to "appropriate" direction in the current EU harmonization process [1].

The rural women have been most disadvantaged because of male dominated society. They have all the potentials but lack the support and a movement of their own. Unions of women founded through cooperatives provide with significant advantages to empower women in all the spheres of life. These women's unions, helped women to become stronger in the countryside, have increased rapidly in recent years in Turkey. Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative is one of the organizations.

The Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative is a rural area organization formed by a limited number of women that actualized their entrepreneurship objectives in a village abandoned due to migration [2]. This structure, which presents products growing in the village by being processed through various methods for sale, was determined to be important to be analyzed as a model structure.

Cooperatives are able to promote economic and social development because they are commercial organizations that follow a broader set of values than those associated purely with the profit motive [3]. Cooperatives as a model of organization for women have been a very new, exciting, and active subject in Turkey. Women cooperatives are located from Naple to Iran in the world. Especially, in the countries which are underdeveloped economically, women's economic development is important for them [4]. There are a lot of studies dealing with the women's union and cooperatives in worldwide. Prakash [5] evaluated to relationships among rural women, food security and agricultural

cooperatives. Merret and Walzer [6] edited the essays about cooperatives and local development. Vakoufaris et al. [7] focused on women's cooperatives, a form of productive agricultural cooperatives, and their importance and their contribution to local development. Ozdemir [8] highlighted to emerge as an important subject in terms of cooperation and women both taking part in economic life. Meera and Gowda [9] deal with the economic status of women in dairy cooperative societies through changes in their income, access to cash and credit; to understand changes in their confidence in financial transactions; their aspiration for economic autonomy; to draw inferences from the study and make suggestions for economic empowerment of women. Gebremichael [10] identified the roles of agricultural cooperatives in promoting food security and rural women's empowerment. Kebede and Kassa [11] investigated women's participation in cooperatives: With the case of Gedeb Hassasa farmer's multipurpose cooperative society in Arsi Zone, Oromiya, Ethiopia. Maleko and Msuya [12] examined the women participation in cooperatives dealing with the case of selected Saccos and Amcos in Kilimanjaro and Arusha Regions Tanzania, East Africa. Sadeghi et al. [13] investigated the cooperative role of women in running the international program of Carbon Sequestration Project performed by United Nation Development Program (UNDP) in droughty and dessert region of Sarbisheh County – South Xorasan – Iran. Barut [4] revealed the women's cooperatives contributions to local region economy with case of Seferihisar agricultural cooperative development model, Turkey.

The Women Shareholders of Vakıflı village Development Cooperative and their entrepreneurship activities were analyzed in this study and the study was conducted in order to understand their aim of establishment, which products they choose to present them for sale and how they supply these products, their level of awareness and to set forth the relations between the factors that affect them [14-18]. The members of this cooperative living in the Village of Vakıflı were interviewed for these purposes. The women's educational and income levels, their wish to leave the village or stay in the village, traditional agricultural information, the purpose of use of their income other than the sale of products and the benefits of the cooperative as well as the expectations of the cooperative members for

future were determined and evaluated accordingly.

2. THE DATA AND METHODS

The main material of the study is the questionnaire data acquired from the face-to-face interviews. Additionally previous studies on this issue and concerning records and statistics were taken advantage. A questionnaire was implemented in Vakıflı Village which is an Armenian village within the borders of Samandağ District of the Hatay Province with the members of the Women Shareholders of the Development Cooperative (Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative). 27 women that mean the entire members of the cooperation were interviewed in accordance with the full count method. The data was evaluated with percentage distribution and arithmetic means.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic Profile

The Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative consists of 27 members. As it will be mentioned while interpreting many future findings, the population of the village has decreased a lot due to migration. The population of the village is 124 as of 2014 [19].

Findings defining the members of this foundation, which is a model of the organized women entrepreneurship in rural area which is the subject of the study, with some of their socio-demographic characteristics, are primarily set forth in the study.

Ages of the women differ from 32 to 60 and the mean age is around 43. This mean indicates that it is generally youngsters who migrate from the village. The youngest member of the cooperative is 32 years old and women are generally middle aged. The majority of them are married (88,89%). Families of women consist of 5 averagely. The magnitude of the families differs from 3 persons to 7 persons. Families do not vary radically in terms of their magnitude.

There are not any illiterate women among the women interviewed or any women who did not receive education on a literate level, women are primary education graduates at the least and

more than half of them are secondary school graduates (51,85%). High school graduates follow the secondary school graduates with a rate of one out of three (33,33%) and the primary school graduates has the lowest rate (14,81%). This distribution demonstrates a very high education profile compared to the women educational rates in rural areas in Turkey. 15,57% of women above 15 years are illiterate based on the towns and villages in Turkey as of 2014, 15,55% of them are literate and 37,61% of them are primary school graduates. The rate of the high school and secondary school graduates is 26,56%. In this case more than two out of three (68,73%) are primary school graduates at the most [20]. According to these results, the interviewed women have a very high educational level compared to the general women education status in Turkey.

Some findings about the economic aspects of the women and their families are as in the Table 2.

Annual average income of families is 6612,57 US\$ and the average income per capita is 1 562,30 US\$. The family with the lowest income has an annual average income of 3 664,92 US\$ and the family with the highest income has an annual average income of 11 518,32 US\$. Annual household income average of Turkey for rural areas in 2013 is around 11 305, 76 US\$ [21,22]. The average income of the study field is observed to be lower than the average income of Turkey. The cultural income's share within the total income is 67,71%. This data shows that agriculture is a very important occupation.

One of the common constraints is lack of access to opportunities of earning income and to credit which is generally a major obstacle to the improvement of women's economic situation [23]. Looking at the data regarding income sources; two sources that provide income for the entire families of the interviewed women are agriculture and the sale of the

Table 1. Some socio- demographic characteristics of women

Socio-demographic criteria			
Age	Mean age	42,96	
	Age range	32 – 60	
		Frequency	Rate (%)
Marital status	Married	24	88,89
	Single	3	11,11
	Total	27	100,00
Family magnitude	Average individual number	4,52	
	Top and bottom limit	3-7	
		Frequency	Rate (%)
Education	Primary	4	14,81
	Secondary	14	51,85
	High school	9	33,33
	Total	27	100,00

Table 2. Some findings regarding the economical situations of the women and their families

Some economic criteria		(US\$)	
Annual income (US\$)	Average income	6 612,57	
	Income range	3 664,92 – 11 518,32	
	Average income per capita	1 562,30	
	Income range per capita	732,98 – 3 141,36	
	Average agricultural income	4 452,36	
	Share of the agricultural income in the general income (%)	67,71	
		Frequency	Rate (%)
Income sources	Agriculture	27	100,00
	Cooperative product sale	27	100,00
	Rent	3	11,11
	Salary-wage	2	7,41
	Total	27	*

*This question exceeds a hundred since more than one answer were received

cooperative products. The rate of the income sources other than these is rather limited (renting, salary-wage). This data indicates that cooperative sale also provides important amounts of incomes for the families of these women.

3.2 Economic Activities of Women

All of the women remarked that their families produce aiming at the Market. Products aimed at the Market are demonstrated in the Table 3. Citrus, squash, grape and walnut are the products produced the most. Citrus fruits are produced by 70,37% of the families, grapes by more than the half (55,56%) and squashes by almost the half (44,44%).

Table 3. Products produced for the Market and their rate of being produced by the families of the women (*)

	Frequency	Rate (%)
Citrus	19	70,37
Grape	15	55,56
Pumpkin	12	44,44
Walnut	9	33,33
Daffodil	7	25,93
Pomegranate	7	25,93
Japanese plum	5	18,52
Fig	5	18,52
Bergamot	4	14,81
Mulberry	2	7,41
Blackberry	2	7,41

This question exceeds a hundred since more than one answer were received

Women were asked if they attend the agricultural activities and it is determined that they are engaged in the agricultural activities completely. 85,19% remark they attend some of the activities and 14,81% attend all of the activities.

The magnitude of the average cultivated area where the families of the women carry out their agricultural production is 8,92 decares and almost all of it (95,07%) is cultivated as property land. The smallest cultivated area is 5 and the biggest cultivated area is 16 decares. As it can be interpreted that the lands which families have and process is pretty small scaled. This can be evaluated as the reason of low income and the explanatory finding of the migration from rural areas to cities.

One of the factors that affect the social status of women and their entrepreneurship is their

involvement in the social security [24]. All of the interviewed women in the cooperation stated that they have social security. The fact that they have social security although they have low average incomes can be interpreted as an indication that they possess awareness in this term. It is stated that almost all of the women employed in the agriculture sector are excluded from the social security system [24]. The type of social security is Bağ-Kur (Social Security Organization for Artisans and the Self-Employed), SSK (Social Security Authority) and the retirement fund with the rates of 81,48%, 14,82% and 3,70% respectively¹. There are no women with private insurance or green card.

3.3 Membership to Cooperatives

How the women became members of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative and for how long they have been members are specified in the Table 4. 18,52% of these women are observed to be leaders of this organization and 11,11% of them joined the organization in a very short time. However; more than half of the women (59,26%) joined the cooperative and its activities after waiting for a while. The rate of those who became members very late is low and consequently almost all of the women living in the village got involved in the organization. This can be associated with the success of the cooperative and its activities because women got involved the most by observing the activities of the cooperative for a while, seeing its success and after their concerns are removed. Results in the Table 4 support these findings.

Table 4. The ways the women joined the cooperation

	Frequency	Rate (%)
I participated in its establishment actively and became a member	5	18,52
I became a member just after its foundation	3	11,11
I waited for a while before joining, then became a member	16	59,26
I became a member very late	3	11,11
Total	27	100,00

¹ At present, these types of social security are united under the name of Social Security Institution (<http://www.sgk.gov.tr>).

Women who joined the cooperation after a certain amount of time from its foundation were asked why they did not join in the beginning and why they joined later and the answers are specified in the Table 4. Those who say "I became a member just after its foundation" were also regarded in the group of those who joined in the foundation process and 19 women who joined later were included in the evaluation.

3.4 Economic Activities Carried Out Through Cooperatives

According to the Table 5, 42,11% of women stated that they did not believe the women shareholders of the cooperative and the activities to be carried out by it would be successful and 15,79% of them did not believe that it would not provide a good income.

Subsequent membership of women who said "my husband did not let me" indicates that the ideas of their husbands changed positively.

Reasons for becoming members later on show that the activities of the women shareholders of the cooperative have become successful since its foundation. Those who became members later were generally affected by the success of the cooperative and thought the income was substantial. This proves the entrepreneur or the leader role's importance. Especially the 5 women who were actively involved in the foundation process of the cooperative have great importance.

Products being produced and sold by the members of the Women Shareholders of the

Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative are available in the Table 6. Women sell the agricultural products they produced by turning them into jam or drinks such as liqueur. It is seen that products turned into jam the most are Pumpkin, Sour Orange, Orange and Walnut. Women were asked if they had any education or training regarding the production of these products and it was seen that all of the women produce these homemade products peculiar to themselves with traditional methods. None of them previously had any training.

The answer to the question of how much time these women spare for the production of the products that they present for sale is analyzed. Women averagely spend 5 days of the week (4,62 days) and 3,78 hours in a day for the production of the products. While this is the average, there are women who spend 2 days or 7 days of the week for these occupations. The average of 4 and 5 days (62,96%) is dense on the daily basis and the occupation hour differs from 3 to 5 hours while the majority (85,19%) states that they spare 3 or 4 hours for this job within the day.

The level of the income was tried to be determined as a result of this production. Women acquire 303,70 TL averagely in a month. While women do not implement the production in a specific place collectively or together, they sell the products which they produce according to their preferences in a common sale area. This is why they acquire income depending on their production. The woman that acquires the least amount receives 150 TL while the one acquiring the highest amount receives 550 TL in a month.

Table 5. Reasons why women joined the cooperative after a certain amount of time from its foundation joined late

Reasons for not joining in the beginning	Frequency	Rate (%)
I did not think it would be successful	8	42,11
My husband did not let me	8	42,11
I did not lean towards it	6	31,58
I did not think it would provide any substantial income	3	15,79
I thought I would not have time	2	10,53
Reasons for joining later		
I saw it provides remarkable income	12	63,16
I saw it was becoming successful	7	36,84
My member friends convinced me	5	26,32
I did not want to be excluded because everyone joined	3	15,79
Those who joined the cooperation after a certain amount of time from its foundation	19	*

*This question exceeds a hundred since more than one answer were received

The most intense income range is 250-350. 77,78% of the women acquires an income amount of 250 to 350 monthly. The rate of those who receives less than this is 11,11% and the same rate applies to the women acquiring the highest amount of income. Women leave a certain amount of share for the Cooperative from their income. The incomes specified here is the amount that is left for the member after the cooperative share is dropped.

Table 6. Products being produced and sold by the cooperative member women

	Frequency	Percentage
Pumpkin jam	12	44,44
Sour orange jam	11	40,74
Orange syrup	10	37,04
Walnut jam	10	37,04
Liqueur	7	25,93
Pomegranate jam	9	33,33
Fig jam	5	18,52
Plum jam	5	18,52
Blackberry jam	2	7,41
Bergamot jam	4	14,81
Mandarin syrup	3	11,11
Mulberry syrup	2	7,41
Wine	1	3,70

* This question exceeds a hundred since more than one answer were received

The distribution of the answer to the question of how significant these incomes are for the budget of the women and their families are available in the Table 7. The income acquired was regarded as an important income source by more than half of the women (55,56%) and as a small contribution to my family by almost half of them (44,44%). This difference may emerge from the income amount that women acquire from the cooperative sales or the difference of the share of it in their budget. However, the incomes they acquire contribute to the budget of all of their families.

Table 7. Position of the income you acquire through the cooperative in the family budget

	Frequency	Percentage
An important income source	15	55,56
A small contribution to my family	12	44,44
Total	27	100,00

Women act together in the marketing process and maintain the sale operations as a monopoly.

This why the answers to the questions about the production sale are common and consequently percentage was not used for these questions and they are summarized as the common statement of women.

According to the statements of women their buyers are generally local tourists visiting the touristic areas in vicinity. Rather than men, women generally buy these products and youngsters demand the products more in terms of the age group. Additionally there are some permanent buyers of the products and the women sell their product to their permanent customers with the order receiving method. Orders in this group are the domestic orders and they send their product to some small sale points especially through Istanbul. They stated they found the sale points in Istanbul via their relatives and they kept selling because the products were found satisfying. Settlements around have also demands for the products but they are very limited. Other than this, women introduce their products by participating in various fairs implemented on organic products, local products and traditional products etc. Another method to sell or find customers is introducing their products via the web page they created and allowing them to see the products. They try to meet the order they receive this way too.

It is searched if all of the women are actively involved in these types of sale operations or if these strategies are formulated by women who stand out with their entrepreneurship or by some mutual effort. The rate of the women who stated that they are always actively involved in the product sale operations is determined to be 14,81% while the rate for those who stated they occasionally participate in these activities is 29,63%. More than the half of the women (55,56%) remarked they never participate in the sale operations. Two of the women who are always active in sale operations are women who were actively involved in the establishment process of the women shareholders of the cooperative and while one of them joined the cooperative after a certain amount of time and the other joined the cooperative late.

3.5 Social Effects of Cooperatives

The types of the changes and effects emerged in the lives of the women in the village with commence of the activities of the formation of the women shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative are available in the Table 7.

As the individuals continuing to live in the village and the members of the cooperative women were asked about their ideas regarding migration. The majority of the women (92,59%) never planned to migrate or planned it rarely. However; 7,42% of them stated they thought about migration. There are no member women who consider migrating in a manner that the idea will be actualized. The reasons of their said attitude or preference to stay in the village were asked. Almost all of the women (96,29%) stated that they were content with the rural lifestyle and never considered migrating from the village or considered it rarely.

Insights of the women regarding the question if the establishment of the women shareholders of the development cooperation has something to do with the general social structure of the village and if yes what kind of effects it formed are available in the Table 8.

All of the women think that the cooperative affected the village in general. Looking at the distribution of what kinds of effects they believe it created; the highest rate (92,59%) belongs to the effect that contribute to the promotion of the village. The majority of women stated that their village became popular because of the production and sale activities of the cooperative. Another effect is that it created social dynamism for the village and this dynamism can be regarded as an important value for a village the population of which decreased due to migration. Another effect as mentioned by 62,96% of the women is the contribution of it to the opportunities of the village. Detailed information was not able to be obtained regarding these opportunities. Again almost half of the women (48,15%) think that the number of tourists visiting the village increased due to the cooperative but the rate of the women who think that the effect on the population decrease of the village is low.

Table 8. Insights of the women regarding migration from the village to cities and the effects of the establishment of the cooperative over the village life

		Frequency	Rate (%)
Have you ever considered migrating from the village to cities or do you consider? If no, what are the reasons?	Never	21	77,78
	Rarely	4	14,81
	Sometimes	2	7,41
	I like living in a village	20	74,07
If no, what are the reasons?	I am happy with the life conditions here	6	22,22
	I don't have the courage to start a live somewhere else	1	3,70
Are there effects of the cooperative on the village?	Yes	27	100,00
	No	0	0,00
What are these effects? (*)	Introduction of the village	25	92,59
	Social dynamism	24	88,89
	More opportunities in the village	17	62,96
	Increase in the number of tourists	13	48,15
	Prevention of the population decrease	3	11,11
Did migration continue after the establishment of the cooperative?	Yes	27	100,00
	No	0	0,00
Does the cooperative have any effects on people to stay in the village?	No	15	55,56
	Partially	12	44,44
Other activities implemented through the cooperative (*)	Charity	22	81,48
	Social activities	21	77,78
	Social meetings	12	44,44
What are the positive values that the Cooperative brought? (*)	Economical contribution	22	81,48
	Synergy in the village	22	81,48
	Positive environment supported by the social dynamism	22	81,48
	Moral satisfaction of acquiring income	15	55,56
Total		27	100,00

**This question exceeds a hundred since more than one answer were received*

There is a part on the web page of Vakıflı Village introducing the women shareholders of the Development Cooperative and this is explained as a major factor of the decrease of migration from the village. Since the decrease of migration has a special importance for the cooperative and the subject of this study, the effect over the migration was also searched. The question whether the migration still continues with the establishment of the cooperative was asked (Table 8). All of the women stated that the migration and the population decrease still continue. 55,56% of women answered none and 44,44% of the women answered partially to the question of what degree the people living in the village have effect on staying in the village.

There are also some social activities of the Women Shareholders of the Development cooperative other than the production activities. The majority of the women participate in the charity activities (81,48%) and social activities (celebrations etc.) (77,78%) and almost half of the women participate in social meetings (44,44%) that they organize for themselves.

The values that the cooperative brought to the lives of women are available in the Table 7 prepared based on the statements of the women. The majority of women (81,48%) mention the acquired economical contribution, the positive environment in the village created by the social dynamism and the increasing synergy. Also the psychological satisfaction that they feel because of their contribution to the family budget is important for more than half of the (55,56%) women.

Insights of the women regarding the future position of the cooperative or the change

directions of its effects are available in the Table 9. The insights and the expectations of the women regarding the future are generally positive. There are no members who think that the positive contributions of the cooperative to them and their families will decrease in the future. All of the women think that these contributions will increasingly continue. Again the majority (92,59%) has positive ideas about the promotion of the village. The rate of those who think it will contribute to the migration positively is not very high (29,63%). The majority thinks the cooperative will not be effective in this term.

Women were asked about the reasons why the migration to cities is so intense and the cooperation cannot be effective in this term. Answers provided are available in the Table 10. According to the women the most important reason for that is the need to reach education opportunities.

The cooperative provided income and social dynamism for the village to some extent. However, the educational needs have not been met. This need is not a factor that can be compensated with personal efforts and that can be ignored when it is impossible to provide it. After that the limited lands in the village and the insignificant income acquired from agriculture are other factors for more than half of the women (55,56%). Also that fact that there is not any chance to acquire income other than agriculture can be interpreted as integrated with the previous factor since it is associated with income. Namely the limited economical opportunities are a reason to migrate. Opposite to these repulsive factors in the village; for some women the attractive characteristics of cities are the economical welfare expectation and the variety of lifestyle

Table 9. Ideas of the women regarding the contributions of the cooperative to their families and the village and its future

		Frequency	Rate (%)
Its effects on the family opportunities	Will continue the same	0	0,00
	Will decrease	0	0,00
	Will increasingly continue	27	100,00
Its effects on the village opportunities	Will continue the same	0	0,00
	Will decrease	0	0,00
	Will increasingly continue	27	100,00
Introduction of the village	Will contribute	25	92,59
	Will not contribute	2	7,41
Prevention of the population decrease of the village	Will contribute	8	29,63
	Will not contribute	19	70,37
Total		27	100,00

Table 10. Reasons why the cooperative is not effective in terms of the migration from the village to cities according to the women

	Frequency	Oran (%)
Search for better educational opportunities	21	77,78
Limited area and littleness of agricultural income	15	55,56
Economical welfare and opportunities in cities	10	37,04
Lack of social activities	8	29,63
Limited income opportunities in the village	5	18,52
Total	27	100,00

opportunities are among the reasons of migration. Women accept that there are developments regarding the income increase and social dynamism thanks to the cooperative activities; however, they remark that this will be a strong effect to stop migration from the village to cities.

4. CONCLUSION

The Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative was tried to be analyzed depending on the data acquired from the questionnaire conducted with the members of this establishment.

Some important results regarding the Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative must be highlighted. These are as follow:

This entity started with only 5 members in the beginning and then women started to be members after seeing the success of the cooperative and its provision of a regular income despite not being so high. This Results of the research indicates the importance of local entrepreneurship and leadership in rural areas. The entrepreneurship and leadership characteristics of women in rural areas must be supported in various ways. Some of them can be training, funding, bureaucratic facilities and awarding. The absence of civil society and leadership training in the rural areas are regarded as factors preventing the conscious leaders to emerge and organization of women in rural areas accordingly. Women especially who were active in the establishment of the cooperative in the Vakıflı Village overcame this obstacle themselves.

One of the objectives of this structure established by women is the prevention or reduction of the said migration. According to

the statements of women the cooperative has not been very effective in this term. However, the results show that the cooperative has been effective in terms of the introduction of the village, social dynamism and the integrity in the village. The point that women reached with their own efforts gives the impression is that they are about to obtain success regarding the migration issue. In other words The cooperative seems to have the potential to prevent the reduction of the population in the village, however; such an amateur effort must be supported by professional and strong hands. Activities such as marketing the products, the production of a range of products and a more effective introduction can be strengthened with the support of the state. This way acquired income may be moved to a level that support the family budget effectively. For areas where especially the rural migration still continues the Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative may be regarded as a model implementations and spread to other areas. The example of the Women Shareholders of the Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative can be used as an important material for the title of "Preparation of the Publications to Introduce Successful Cooperative" which is one of the objectives specified in the action plan prepared by the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock.

Other important matter that should be taken into account is the coverage of the demands and requirements of the population left in the village after the migration. Finally even though the population left in the village is very little livable conditions must be maintained for these areas where people still live. The social dynamism and other positive effects created by the activities implemented by the women members in Vakıflı village are important. Women talk about the increase in the number of tourist after the cooperative

activities. In this content, the activities can be said to have added a new dimension for the agricultural tourism.

As a consequence, three important actions can be mentioned depending on this study in which the Women Shareholders of Vakıflı Village Development Cooperative is analyzed;

- Various supports are required for the maintenance and success of this well-done application,
- Implementation of studies to overcome the obstacles that prevents these activities from being more successful is required and
- The introduction and spread of these examples are very necessary

DISCLAIMER

Some part of this manuscript was previously presented in the following conference.

Conference name: "International Conference Economics".

Date: 18-20 August, 2015;

Location: IRES, Torino, Italy.

Conference link:

["http://torino2015.econworld.org/assets/oruc_uzu_noz_karadogan.pdf"](http://torino2015.econworld.org/assets/oruc_uzu_noz_karadogan.pdf)

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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